

PROFITABILITY ANALYSIS OF SELECTED PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS IN INDIA

Monalisa Panigrahi^{1*} and Gouri Sankar Lall²

1* – Lecturer in Commerce, PG Department of Commerce, Rayagada Autonomous College, Rayagada – 765001

2 – Retired Prof., PG Department of Commerce, Berhampur University, Bhanjabihar, Odisha.

Abstract:

Financial system in country like India is honoured with Banks as its greatest components. Private sector banks are considered as one of the most influential components in uplifting the country's economy and to sustain it is essential to have a brief information regarding the earning capacity which indicates and measures the profitability of the banks with use of profitability ratios. Parameters including Net Profit Margin(NPM), Adjusted cash margin, Return on Equity(ROE), Return on Long term funds and Returns on Assets(ROA) are widely used. The manuscript focusses on ICICI, HDFC, AXIS, YES AND KMB Banks as the sample banks and their profitability is interpreted using various statistical tools. Hypothesis was tested using one way ANOVA. Private sector banks were making tremendous efforts in generating and maintaining profit. Among which HDFC Bank served as the outperformer by leading in profitability.

Keywords: - *Private sector banks, Ratio Analysis, Profitability ratios, ONE WAY ANOVA.*

Introduction:

To facilitate any financial transaction, banks serve as the intermediary agents. They are channels to facilitate financial services such as issue cheques, pay interest on the amount stored and to make offers of loan[1]. Private sector banks are the ones in which the government owns half of ownership in the company. Government regulates these banks and facilitates their financial services [2]. Due to these government ownership, depositors visualise safety of their cash in these banks which indicates a larger customer base. These banks create individual financial plans for their clients yet adhere themselves to the norms of Reserve Bank of India [2]. The total assets of the banking sector got a hike in between 2017-2020. India maintains a well-established, economically superior system in this world. Thus, profitability of top five private sector banks for the financial year 2013-2023 is dealt in this study.

Private Sector Banks:

During 1993, the Banking Regulation Act was amended which added private sector banks to the Indian banking industry. Private sector banks which started their operation after 1991 is referred as New Private sector banks. The criteria for establishment of these banks includes:

- a) The Bank should possess a minimum of Rs 200 crores as its net worth
- b) Out of total paid capital promoters' stake would be at least 25%
- c) Condition of raising the net worth to RS 300 crores in the initial 3 years , mean while offering shares to the public

Research Objective :

Following study was conducted with two research objectives listed below

- I. To evaluate and analyse the profitability performance of the sample banks i.e. ICICI,KMB,HDFC,AXIS and YES Banks
- II. To compare the overall profitability of the sample banks using the profitability parameters like ROE,ROA,NPM,Adjusted cash margin and Return on long term funds

Research Hypothesis:

One way Analysis of Variance [ANOVA] is the statistical tool used for evaluating the sample mean of different banks.

Review of Literature

[1] **Ray and Basak (2022)** have studied the performance of ten private sector banks in India through some parameters of profitability namely ROCE, ROE and NPM over five years ranging from 2017-2021. From the analysis of the study, it has been concluded that HDFC Bank is managing its assets and liabilities considerably well amongst all the selected private sector banks in India.

[2] **Brindadevi (2013)** has analysed the profitability of banks over 10 years from 2002 to 2012. For the analysis and interpretation, the researcher has used various statistical tools and for testing the hypothesis, ONE WAY ANOVA has been applied. From the findings, it is revealed that there was a significant difference among the mean value of NPM, ROE and Interest Spread whereas there was no significant difference found among the mean value of ROA of the sample banks taken in the study.

[3] **Priya(2014)** in her paper analysed the profitability of South Indian Bank, Karur Vysya Bank, AXIS Bank, ICICI Bank through profitability ratio. The objective of the research work was to analyse the overall efficiency of the sample banks over ten years from 2002-2012. To test the hypothesis chi-square test has been used in the study.

[4] **Gaur and Sukhija (2011)** attempted to assess the financial performance of banks in India from the year 2000-2009. The sample banks selected for the research work include ING Vysya Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, Federal Bank Ltd and KMB. The variables used in the study were EPS, ROCE, CAR, Current Ratio, Quick Ratio, Price to Book ratio and Debt to Equity Ratio. The researchers finding revealed that HDFC bank turned out to be more efficient in terms of earnings per share and KMB was found to have a higher price-to-book ratio during the period of the study.

[5] **Sultana et.al. (2020)** studied the profitability of BOB, SBI, ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank from the year 2014-2019. The variables used in the research work were OPM, EPS, NPM, Price-Earnings Ratio and ROCE. The researcher concluded that the public sector banks were profitable in terms of OPM and Price to Earning Ratio whereas private sector banks were found to be profitable in terms of NPM, EPS and ROCE.

Duration of Study:

Data were collected from the secondary sources and the duration of research lies in between FY2013-FY 2023 . Last ten years data were used.

Research Methodology:

This is a Descriptive cum Analytical research mainly emphasising on determining the profitability performance of the previously mentioned sample banks using the Ratio Analysing technique. Various ratios were used such as NPM, ROA, ROE, Adjusted Cash margin, and Return on long term funds. Different statistical tools like Mean, SD and CV were used. The hypothesis were examined by ONE WAY ANOVA and was computed in Microsoft Excel.

Data collection :

One of the most crucial duty of a researcher in a Descriptive cum Analytical research is to collect, interpret, analyse and examine the data. The data were extensively collected from the secondary sources. Other relevant data were gathered through articles, books, journals and annual reports of the used sample banks. Money control and Money Rediff websites are also used for the collection of secondary data.

Limitation of the Study:

The present study comes with the following limitations:

1. Secondary sources were used for data collection
2. Ratio analysis technique is used which is said to have limitations of its own
3. Only profitability ratios are used
4. Due to further unavailability of data, the study is limited with only 5 sample banks such as AXIS, HDFC, KMB, ICICI, YES Banks

Data Presentation and Analysis:

To fulfil all the above mentioned objectives regarding profitability of these private sector banks the data were collected , analysed , presented in the concerned ten year period i.e. FY 2013- FY 2023

NET PROFIT MARGIN:

It is considered to be the percentage of revenue which is left after deducting expenses such as interests, preferred stock dividends, operating costs from the total sales of a company. It is referred to as an important profitability ratio as it depicts the relationship between net profit after taxes and net sales.

$$\text{Net Profit Margin \%} = \text{Net Profit} / \text{Revenue} \times 100.$$

TABLE 1

Year	HDFC	AXIS	ICICI	KMB	YES
2013-14	20.61	20.29	22.20	17.13	16.20
2014-15	21.07	20.73	22.76	19.19	17.32
2015-16	20.41	20.06	18.44	12.75	18.76
2016-17	20.99	8.26	18.09	19.27	20.27
2017-18	21.79	0.60	12.33	20.68	20.84
2018-19	21.29	8.50	5.30	20.32	5.80
2019-20	22.86	2.59	10.60	22.08	-62.98
2020-21	25.74	10.35	20.46	25.94	-17.27
2021-22	28.93	19.33	27.42	31.70	5.60
2022-23	27.29	11.24	29.20	31.93	3.16
Mean	23.098	12.195	18.68	22.099	2.77
S.D	2.92529	7.150489	7.101423	5.807926	24.540840
C.V	12.664689	58.6345961	38.0161830	26.28139734	885.95090

Source :- Retrieved from <http://moneycontrol.com> & <https://money.rediff.com>

[6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15]

Table 1 indicates the bank-wise Mean, SD and CV of Net Profit Margin of selected banks. Out of the sample banks, HDFC Bank registers the highest mean value (23.098) followed by KMB (22.099), ICICI Bank (18.68), Axis Bank (12.195) and YES Bank (2.77) indicating the lowest mean value. At the same time, HDFC Bank has the least degree of variability in terms of NPM with a SD of 2.92529 and CV of 12.664689% and YES Bank has the highest degree of variability with a SD of 24.540840 and CV of 885.95090% indicating an inconsistency in maintaining its profit.

HYPOTHESIS

H0 : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$ There is no notable difference between NPM of selected private-sector banks in India

H1 : $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 \neq \mu_5$ There is a notable difference between NPM of selected private-sector banks in India

Table - 2

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F.	Mean Square	F (Cal.)	Table Value at 5% level of significance
Between Samples	2840.045372	4	710.011343	4.282325	2.578739
Within Samples	165.800428	45	165.800428		

Computed using MS. Excel

The above table indicates that the calculated value of F (4.282325) is greater than the table value (2.578739), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. In light of the result, it is concluded that there is a notable difference in the NPM of selected private sector banks in India.

ADJUSTED CASH MARGIN:

Used for measuring and examining the ability and efficiency of a company to convert sales into cash, also called as Operating cash flow margin. Adjusted Cash flow margin provides a brief insights on a company’s profitability by comparing its net sales with operating cash flow.

$$\text{Adjusted cash margin} = \text{Cash Flow from Operations} / \text{Net sales}$$

Year	HDFC	AXIS	ICICI	KMB	YES
2013-14	18.65	17.29	19.02	16.40	14.36
2014-15	18.91	17.70	19.31	17.52	15.34
2015-16	18.31	17.21	15.31	12.51	16.31
2016-17	18.85	7.44	14.33	17.48	17.01
2017-18	19.26	1.48	10.44	18.43	17.47
2018-19	19.05	7.90	5.31	18.32	5.90
2019-20	19.88	3.07	9.73	19.56	-42.40
2020-21	22.19	9.60	17.60	22.69	-13.29
2021-22	24.52	16.99	23.36	26.81	6.57
2022-23	24.04	22.30	25.74	27.58	4.30
Mean	20.366	12.098	16.015	19.73	4.157
S.D	2.2104804	6.7252595	5.9953235	4.4427626	17.888892
C.V	10.85377	55.589845	37.435675	22.5178033	430.331777

Table - 3

Source :- Retrieved from <http://moneycontrol.com> & <https://money.rediff.com>

[6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15]

Table 3 indicates the Bank-wise Mean, SD and CV of Adjusted cash margin of the selected banks. Out of all the five private sector banks, HDFC Bank registers the highest average adjusted cash margin (20.366) followed by KMB (19.73), ICICI Bank (16.015), AXIS Bank (12.098) and YES Bank (4.157) indicating the lowest average adjusted cash margin. The degree of variability of adjusted cash margin is lowest in the case of HDFC Bank with a SD of 2.2104804 and CV of 10.85377% indicating a greater degree of stability whereas YES Bank has the highest degree of variability with a SD of 17.888892 and CV of 430.331777% indicating an inconsistency in maintaining its profit.

HYPOTHESIS

H0 : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$ There is no notable difference in the Adjusted Cash Margin of selected private-sector banks in India.

H1 : $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 \neq \mu_5$ There is a notable difference in the Adjusted Cash Margin of selected private-sector banks in India.

Table - 4

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F.	Mean Square	F (Cal.)	Table Value at 5% level of significance
Between Samples	1768.017428	4	442.004357	4.6711449	2.578739
Within Samples	165.800428	45	165.800428		

Computed using MS. Excel

The above table indicates that the calculated value of F (4.6711449) is greater than the table value (2.578739), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. In light of the results, it is concluded that there is a notable difference in the Adjusted Cash Margin of selected private sector banks in India.

RETURN ON LONG TERM FUND

Long term profitability of a firm is measured through this profitability ratio. It describes the ability of a company to generate profit from its long term resources by comparing earning before the interest and tax to its long term fund.

Return on Long term fund % = EBIT / Long term fund

Table – 5

Year	HDFC	AXIS	ICICI	KMB	YES
2013-14	81.47	73.36	56.92	59.62	134.67
2014-15	66.77	72.32	57.03	58.89	94.12
2015-16	70.54	68.74	50.29	52.62	92.35
2016-17	65.17	57.23	45.09	53.30	71.05
2017-18	62.88	43.00	38.54	43.84	72.69
2018-19	55.57	60.36	38.13	46.78	82.41
2019-20	55.69	49.83	49.01	43.32	-7.20
2020-21	47.92	42.53	41.76	32.64	23.73
2021-22	43.64	44.88	41.61	29.78	40.28
2022-23	47.54	47.30	45.46	32.45	38.94
Mean	59.719	55.955	46.384	45.324	64.304
S.D	11.2211750	11.568820	6.502728	10.40114436	38.7945398
C.V	18.789957	20.675221159	14.019336	22.948425	60.329901

Source :- Retrieved from <http://moneycontrol.com> & <https://money.rediff.com>

[6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15]

Table 5 indicates the bank-wise Mean, SD and CV of Return on Long term funds of selected banks. Out of all the five private sector banks, YES Bank has the highest mean value (64.304) followed by HDFC Bank (59.719), AXIS Bank (55.955), ICICI Bank (46.384) and KMB (45.324) indicating the lowest return on long-term fund. The degree of variability of ICICI Bank is lowest with a SD of 6.502728 and CV of 14.019336% whereas YES Bank registers the highest degree of variability with a SD of 38.7945398 and CV of 60.329901% indicating an inconsistency in maintaining its profit.

HYPOTHESIS

H0 : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$ There is no notable difference in the Return on Long-term funds of selected private sector banks in India.

H1 : $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 \neq \mu_5$ There is a notable difference in the Return on Long-term funds of selected private sector banks in India.

Table - 6

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F.	Mean Square	F (Cal.)	Table Value at 5% level of significance
Between Samples	2754.093148	4	688.523287	1.6177387	2.578739
Within Samples	19152.37986	45	425.608441		

Computed using MS. Excel

The above table indicates that the calculated value of F (1.6177387) is less than the table value (2.578739), thereby accepting the null hypothesis. In light of the result, it is concluded that there is no notable difference in the Return on long-term funds of selected private sector banks in India.

RETURN ON EQUITY

It is the ratio which evaluates the capacity of a company to generate profit from the investment's done by the shareholders

Return on Net worth % = Profit after tax / Equity share holder fund.

Table – 7

Year	HDFC	AXIS	ICICI	KMB	YES
2013-14	19.50	16.26	13.39	12.23	22.71
2014-15	16.47	16.46	13.89	13.19	17.16
2015-16	16.91	15.46	11.19	8.72	18.41
2016-17	16.26	6.59	10.11	12.35	15.09
2017-18	16.45	0.43	6.63	10.89	16.40
2018-19	14.12	7.01	3.19	11.47	6.39
2019-20	15.35	1.91	6.99	12.25	-75.56
2020-21	15.27	6.48	11.21	11.01	-10.42
2021-22	15.39	11.30	13.94	11.90	3.15
2022-23	15.74	7.63	16.13	13.17	1.76
Mean	16.146	8.953	10.667	11.718	1.509
S.D	1.3522366	5.4503872	3.807377181	1.2445545	27.3765908
C.V	8.3750567	60.877775	35.69304566	10.620878	1814.2207

Retrieved from <http://moneycontrol.com> & <https://money.rediff.com>

[6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15]

Table – 7 shows the bank-wise Mean, SD and CV of ROE of selected banks. Out of all the five private sector banks, HDFC Bank has the highest mean value (16.146) followed by KMB (11.718), ICICI Bank (10.667), Axis Bank (8.953) and YES Bank (1.509) indicating the lowest return on equity. At the same time, the degree of variability of KMB Bank is the lowest with a SD of 1.2445545 and CV of 10.620878% whereas the degree of variability of YES Bank is the highest with a SD of 27.3765908 and CV of 1814.2207%.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀ : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$ There is no notable difference in the ROE of selected private sector banks in India.

H1 : $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 \neq \mu_5$ There is a notable difference in the ROE of selected private sector banks in India.

Table - 8

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F.	Mean Square	F (Cal.)	Table Value at 5% level of significance
Between Samples	1141.602092	4	285.400523	1.61130344	2.578739
Within Samples	7970.58031	45	177.12400688		

Computed using MS. Excel

The above table indicates that the calculated value of F (1.61130344) is less than the table value (2.578739), thereby accepting the null hypothesis. In light of the result, it is concluded that there is no notable difference in the ROE of selected private sector banks in India.

RETURN ON ASSETS

It is a type of profitability ratio which denotes the capacity of a company / firm to generate return from all its overall resources. It also determines the relationship between total assets and net profit.

Return on asset % = Net profit / Total asset

Table – 9

Year	HDFC	AXIS	ICICI	KMB	YES
2013-14	1.72	1.62	1.64	1.71	1.48
2014-15	1.73	1.59	1.72	1.76	1.47
2015-16	1.73	1.56	1.34	1.08	1.53
2016-17	1.68	0.61	1.26	1.58	1.54
2017-18	1.64	0.03	0.77	1.54	1.35
2018-19	1.69	0.58	0.34	1.55	0.45
2019-20	1.71	0.17	0.72	1.65	-6.36
2020-21	1.78	0.66	1.31	1.81	-1.26
2021-22	1.78	1.10	1.65	1.99	0.33
2022-23	1.78	0.72	2.01	2.23	0.20
Mean	1.724	0.864	1.276	1.69	0.073
S.D	0.04454211	0.549858163	0.4954836021	0.28795833031	2.306980927
C.V	2.58364907	63.64099108	38.8310032	17.0389544	3160.2478452

Source: Retrieved from <http://moneycontrol.com> & <https://money.rediff.com>

[6] [7] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15]

Table – 9 shows the bank-wise Mean, SD and CV of ROA of selected Bank. Out of all the five private sector banks, the HDFC Bank has the highest mean value (1.724) followed by KMB (1.69), ICICI Bank (1.276), Axis Bank (0.864) and YES Bank (0.073) indicating the lowest average ROA. At the same time, the degree of variability of HDFC Bank is the lowest with a SD of 0.04454211 and CV of 2.58364907%, Whereas YES Bank registers highest degree of variability with a SD of 2.306980927 and CV of 3160.2478452%.

HYPOTHESIS

H0 : $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = \mu_3 = \mu_4 = \mu_5$ There is no notable difference in the ROA of selected private sector banks in India.

H1 : $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2 \neq \mu_3 \neq \mu_4 \neq \mu_5$ There is a notable difference in the ROA of selected private sector banks in India.

Table - 10

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	D.F.	Mean Square	F (Cal.)	Table Value at 5% level of significance
Between Samples	18.756512	4	4.689128	3.543473	2.578739
Within Samples	59.54913	45	1.323314		

Computed using MS. Excel

The above table indicates that the calculated value of F (3.543473) is greater than the table value (2.578739), there by rejecting the null hypothesis. In light of the results, it is concluded that there is a notable difference in the ROA of selected private sector banks in India.

FINDINGS

1. The NPM reveals that HDFC Bank has the highest mean value of 23.098 implying effective management of its costs and consistency in maintaining its profit throughout the period of the study. Whereas YES Bank has the lowest mean value of 2.77 indicating least management over its cost and inconsistency in maintaining its profit. To conclude the hypothesis, there is a notable difference in the NPM of selected private sector banks in India.
2. The Adjusted Cash Margin shows that HDFC Bank registers the highest average adjusted cash margin of 20.366 indicating greater efficiency in converting sales into cash, whereas YES Bank indicates the lowest average adjusted cash margin of 4.157 over a period of ten years thereby showing the inability of the management to covert sales in to cash. To conclude the hypothesis, there is a notable difference in the adjusted cash margin of selected private sector banks in India.
3. The Return on Long term fund of YES Bank is the highest with a mean value of 64.304 indicating better utilisation of its long-term fund in generating revenue and net profit and KMB indicates the lowest return on long term funds with a mean value of 45.324. To conclude the hypothesis there is no notable difference in the Return on Long-term fund of selected private sector banks in India.
4. The ROE reveals that HDFC Bank has the highest return on equity with a mean value of 16.146 which shows that it provided good returns to its shareholders over ten years and YES Bank has the lowest return on equity with a least mean value of 1.509. To conclude the hypothesis, there is no notable difference in the ROE among different private sector banks in India.
5. The ROA of HDFC Bank is found to be highest with a mean value of 1.724 indicating better utilisation of assets to earn profit than other banks and YES Bank was found to have a very low return on assets with a mean value of 0.073 thereby not able to utilise its assets wisely. To conclude the hypothesis there is a notable difference in the ROA of selected private sector banks in India.

Conclusion:

In this competitive era, there are a list of challenges in front of private sector banks one of which is to maintain a constant profit. The main aim of the study is to inform and make the customers aware regarding the performance of banks. Time to time evaluation indicates the efficiency and consistency of banks in generating profits, performing better and turn out to be successful in the field of banking industry. Today private sector banks serve as the major pillar in maintaining the economy of the country. Innovation in technology adds major perks in better utilisation of the resources and thus maintains a proper balance between social responsibility and overall profitability. In this study five private sector banks were taken and were evaluated using different ratios or parameters. Results revealed that all the banks were making continuous efforts to provide maximum benefits to the end users and also in maintaining the consistency. Out of all the five major chosen private sector banks, HDFC Bank served as an outperformer leading in profitability through out the study period.

References

1. Ray, P., & Basak, C. S. (2022). PERFORMANCE VARIATION OF PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS IN INDIA BASED ON PROFITABILITY PARAMETERS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY.
2. Brindadevi, V. (2013). A study on profitability analysis of private sector banks in India. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 13(4), 45-50.
3. Priya, S. (2014). An Analysis of profitability position of private sector banks in India. *International journal of business and Management invention*, 3(2), 45-53.
4. Gaur, A., & Sukhija, S. (2011). A study of financial performance of selected private banks in India. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research in Business Management*, 2(4), 214-232.
5. Sultana, A., Reddy, T. N., & Krishna, U. G. (2020). Profitability Analysis of Public and Private Sector banks in India—A Fundamental Approach. *Journal of Mechanics of Continua and Mathematical Sciences*, spl5 (5), 159-170.
6. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/hdfcbank/ratiosVI/HDF01>
7. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/axisbank/ratiosVI/AB16>
8. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/icicibank/ratiosVI/ICi02%23ICi02>
9. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/kotakmahindrabank/ratiosVI/KMB>
10. <https://www.moneycontrol.com/financials/yesbank/ratiosVI/YB>
11. <https://money.rediff.com/companies/HDFC-Bank-Ltd/14030055/ratio>
12. <https://money.rediff.com/companies/ICICI-Bank-Ltd/14030056/ratio>
13. <https://money.rediff.com/companies/Axis-Bank-Ltd/14030047/ratio>
14. <https://money.rediff.com/companies/Kotak-Mahindra-Bank-Ltd/14060005/ratio>
15. <https://money.rediff.com/companies/YES-Bank-Ltd/14030144/ratio>